

A Methodology and Replication Roadmap for Designing Digital Twins in Additive Manufacturing

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Abstract

The industrial adoption of Digital Twins (DTs) for optimizing Additive Manufacturing processes is frequently hindered by the lack of standardized, reproducible frameworks. This report addresses this gap by proposing a structured methodology for the design and deployment of an end-to-end Digital Twin (DT) architecture for Laser Powder Bed Fusion (LPBF) processes. The core of this methodology is the synergistic fusion of two components: a physics-based simulation model based on Finite Element Model (FEM) that captures the complex physics phenomena of the process, and an AI-powered model for in-situ visual defect detection during the printing process. The entire system is orchestrated by a microservices backbone utilizing containerization and a modular big-data architecture that is realized via an event-driven message broker that ensures seamless data communication and interoperability. The aim of this work is to provide a clear, actionable guide and a generalized replication roadmap as a blueprint for researchers and engineers to systematically develop and deploy sophisticated digital twin systems, thereby bridging the gap between theoretical concepts and industrial viability.

1 Introduction

The potential of Digital Twins (DTs) in Additive Manufacturing (AM) is widely acknowledged, yet the lack of standardized methodologies hinders their widespread adoption and replication. The

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development of a DT is often a bespoke, non-reproducible effort, making it time consuming and expensive to produce components with sound structure and good mechanical properties. To overcome the prevalent trial-and-error approach, a more systematic process is needed to optimize process parameters, monitor for faults and handle the large volume of data inherent in modern manufacturing applications. This report addresses this challenge by presenting a structured, step-by-step methodology for designing, and implementing a Digital Twin for Laser Powder Bed Fusion (LPBF) processes. The implementation of this methodology, which has been successfully applied in the Twin4Twin project [1], is generalized into a replication roadmap that serves as a blueprint for the AM community. The primary contribution of this work is a practical, step-by-step methodology that facilitates a more structured, less monolithic approach to DT development, promoting reusability and accelerating the path from research to industrial deployment.

2 Background and Related Work

This section presents briefly the background information and related literature on Digital Twins in AM applications. A recent systematic literature review on DTs in 3D printing, structured using the PICOC framework to capture printer types, maturity levels and methodologies, along with challenges and applications is given in [2]. A comprehensive review, highlighting how DTs facilitate real-time monitoring, defect detection, predictive maintenance and process optimization through sensor integration and data capture is presented in [3]. Ramman et al, also deliver a systematic review exploring DT applications in real-time monitoring, simulation and ML within AM emphasizing the role of intelligent and adaptable DTs in optimizing manufacturing processes [4].

3 Methodology for Digital Twin Development

The literature review highlights several research gaps that motivate this work. First, current studies rarely integrate DT technologies with advanced simulation models and there are very few works that explore real-time data processing and Machine Learning (ML) techniques for adaptive process control and anomaly detection. Moreover, existing approaches often lack robust quality assurance frameworks capable of performing real time defect detection. Finally, much of the existing work presents DTs in a generic form without detailed descriptions on practical deployment in industrial AM applications. The proposed methodology deconstructs the development of Digital Twins (DTs) for AM applications into systematic, replicable and modular framework. It is designed to address the key challenges consistently highlighted in the relevant literature, i.e. the lack of standardized DT design processes and the limited reproducibility of existing implementations.

The presented approach structures DT development into five sequential and interdependent phases, each of which can be independently validated at subsystem level, i.e. before system-level integration. Such modularity facilitates reproducibility, scalability and cross-domain applicability across AM processes.

Phase I: Physical Interface and Data Acquisition

The foundational stage that establishes a reliable connection and synchronization between the physical domain and the digital counterpart. The primary goal is to create a comprehensive, synchronized data acquisition system that captures the states of the manufacturing process. This involves instrumenting the testbed, i.e. the 3d printing machine, with a suite of sensors that will allow to monitor the process states. These include pyrometers for capturing the thermal data, various sensors for parameters like gas flow and pressure, and a high-resolution camera for layer-wise powder bed imaging. A crucial architectural decision at this stage is the implementation of a dual-pipeline data collection and storage strategy. High-velocity, low-volume time-series data is directed to a real-time streaming pipeline, while high-volume, low-frequency image data is persisted to an object storage system. This design prevents data bottlenecks and optimizes data processing for each distinct type.

Phase II: Physics-based Modelling

Following instrumentation, the second stage focuses on physics-based modelling to create a realistic simulation model that serves as the predictive core of the DT. The objective here is to develop a simulation model that captures the complex, multi-physics phenomena of Laser Powder Bed Fusion (LPBF) [5]. This is achieved by developing a high-fidelity, thermo-mechanical Finite Element Model (FEM) [6] using a tool such as Abaqus. The model simulates the layer-by-layer material deposition, heat transfer, and subsequent stress accumulation to precisely predict final part distortion. While highly accurate, the FEM is computationally prohibitive, and time consuming making it unsuitable for real-time applications. Therefore, its primary purpose is to serve as the definitive benchmark for calibrating and validating the lightweight surrogate model developed in the subsequent stage.

Phase III: Reduced Order Model Generation

To overcome the computational limitations of the high-fidelity model, the third stage involves the generation of a surrogate model from the FEM datasets, creating a Reduced Order Model (ROM) that serves as the real-time physics engine. The goal is to produce a computationally efficient model capable of simulating part distortion and stress. In our Twin4Twin use-case we employ model order reduction techniques, specifically based on Tensor Rank Decomposition (TRD), to create a ROM from the high-fidelity FEM simulation data. TRD is a mathematical method whose main strength lies in the full interpretability of its result, i.e. the contribution of each variable to a system's outcome can be isolated and interpreted separately from other components. The outcome is a lightweight physics engine that can provide predictions in approximately 15 seconds or less, rather than hours, enabling rapid "what-if" analysis and forecasting.

Phase IV: Data-centric AI Development

Complementing the physics-based models with data-driven AI models, which builds the AI-powered engine of the DT system. This stage aims to develop an AI model capable of automatically detecting visual surface defects from camera imagery in real time. At this stage there are two options, first is to use an open-source deep learning model, already pretrained with huge amount of open data, in a zero-shot mode, or finetune one with your own images. Of course, this requires human annotation by experts in order to create an initial dataset with adequate quality labels that represent real defects. The outcome of this phase is an AI-Powered Module that serves as a layer-wise defect detection system.

Phase V: System Integration and Orchestration

The final step is the architectural integration that brings all developed components together into a cohesive and operational DT framework. The goal is to create a scalable, modular, and interoperable DT architecture. To achieve this, we leverage key technologies such as Docker [7] to containerize each module (the ROM, AI model, and databases), which ensures portability and isolation. Apache Kafka [8] is implemented as the event-driven message broker, serving as the central nervous system that enables seamless, low-latency communication between all components. This integrated flexible architecture ensures that individual modules can be independently updated, scaled, or replaced, ensuring scalability of the DT.

4 Replication Roadmap

The replication roadmap builds upon the methodology described earlier, that has been successfully designed, implemented and tested on a real LPBF use-case. It is translated it into a sequence of actionable steps that can be systematically applied to different AM contexts, with the aim to facilitate reproducibility, modularity and adaptability across different AM technologies and industrial contexts. The replication roadmap is based on the following step-by-step guidelines, where each step addresses a distinct aspect of DT development, with clear entry points and outcomes that ensure reproducibility, adaptability and scalability.

Step 1: Digital maturity level assessment and DT requirements

The first step is the assessment of digital maturity, which establishes the foundation for DT implementation. The goal is to determine the readiness level of AM environment and the testbed monitoring system to support continuous and seamless data exchange between the physical and the digital counterpart. This assessment provides a baseline for the DT intelligence level and selecting the most appropriate operation mode, whether it functions as digital shadow or a fully interactive digital twin. At this stage the DT scope (monitoring, predictive, optimization) should be also clearly defined.

Step 2: Digital Twin architecture selection

Following this, the second step focuses on the architectural selection. The decisions made at previous step regarding the DT intelligence level and its operational mode and depending on the requirements of

the use-case, the DT architecture may prioritize real-time monitoring, predictive operation or closed-loop control functionalities. The outcome of this step is a functional DT architecture with a conceptual information flow diagram visualizing the components and their interactions.

Step 3: Big-data infrastructure

The third step involves the design of the big-data infrastructure that defines how the different data modalities are handled (processed and stored), the standardized data models and the communication pipelines required for real-time data flow. A robust data infrastructure is necessary to handle both high-frequency sensor data streams and high-volume lower frequency image data. By carefully selecting the data storage and the data communication protocols ensures that the critical information is available for real-time inference enabling near real-time decision making.

Step 4: Model development

Fourth and crucial step in DT development is model building, which represents the computational core that gives predictive and simulation capabilities to our DT. Depends on the use-case requirements and the available data different modelling paradigms may be adopted. Physics-bases models, typically build on Finite Element methods, provide high simulation accuracy but limited real-time usability and adaptability in terms of new geometries or material characteristics.

Step 5: Validation and testing

Fifth step is dedicated to validation and testing. Here, models are benchmarked against experimental data, based on Design of Experiments matrix, and validated through uncertainty quantification. Both system-level and component-level validation is performed to ensure that predictions are not only accurate but robust under varying process conditions.

Step 6: Optimization and control

Sixth step focuses on the optimization and control, where the DT is equipped with tools to improve process outcomes. Depending on the use-case requirements and the scenario, these may include optimization routines for process parameters, Bayesian inference methods or model predictive control design for real-time decision making.

Step 7: Deployment and evaluation

Finally, the last step concerns the deployment of the DT, where the DT is integrated into the operational environment to perform real-time inference and decision support. The performance of the DT is evaluated through measurement of KPIs, including, quality improvements, defect detection rates, throughput etc. Continuous monitoring of such KPIs provides feedback for iterative improvements, ensuring the DT remains aligned with evolving production requirements.

5 Conclusions

This report has presented a comprehensive, step-by-step methodology and a modular architectural blueprint for the development of Digital Twins in Additive Manufacturing. By systematically addressing instrumentation, physics-based modeling, data-centric AI development, big data technologies and system integration, we provide a clear and replicable roadmap that mitigates common development challenges. Ultimately, this work serves as a foundational guide for the academic and industrial communities, aiming to accelerate the development and deployment of the next generation of intelligent, resilient, and industrially viable Digital Twins.

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